

Assignment

ON

FODOR'S ESSENTIAL INDIA

INFORMATION SOURCE AND SERVICE (Practice)

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Authority

Title:	Fodor 's Essential India
Publisher:	Fodor's Travel Guides Series
Publication date:	March 2019
Series:	Fodor's Travel Guides Series, #4
Edition Description:	4 th ed.
Pages:	512
Language	English

Introduction

Fodor's India is travel guide book for Republic of India. The First edition came in 1962 with the name Fodor's Guide to India and was edited by Eugene Fodor and William Curtis and published by Fodor's, Modern Guides, New York. Now its name has been changed i.e Fodor's Essential India. The latest edition i.e. 4th edition of this book was published in march 2019 which provides information about the places to visit in India. This guidebook is very helpful for planning trip in India and places are sorted according to state, cuisine, restaurants and other trip planning tools.

Scope

1. Fodor's Essential India is a guide book insider tips for a visit
2. It Include information regarding description of states new hotels and "before you go"
3. This gives fully updated guide
4. Allowing to provide the best travel recommendations for all tastes and budget
5. Fodor's Travel has been a trusted resource offering expert travel advice for every stage traveller's trip

Treatment

1. A spectacular color photo guide captures the ultimate unmissable experiences and attractions throughout India
2. Full-color and full-size street maps throughout will help user can plan efficiently and get around confidently
3. Sample itineraries will help plan and customize an own itinerary so anyone can make the most of the time.
4. Includes tips on where to eat, stay, and shop as well as information about nightlife, sports and the outdoors. "Fodor's Choice" designates our best picks in every category.
5. Full-color feature on getting around India includes indispensable information on buses, trains, taxis, and rickshaws, along with tipping information and an easy-to-use "Travel Times Chart."
6. Convenient overviews show each region and its highlights, and detail-rich chapter planning sections have on-target advice and tips for planning time and for getting around the country by car, bus, and train.
7. Complete with detailed maps and concise descriptions, this India travel guide will help user for planning trip with ease.
8. This give a brief information regarding Sights, Hotels, Restaurant, Shops, Nightlife, Performing Arts Activites.
9. It also provide What's, Where What to eat in India What to drink in India What to buy in India Best Temples and Shrine and Sacred Spaces

Arrangement

1. Fodor's Essential India sorted places of India not in an alphabetical order
2. This book is divided on the basis of Region wise, Know before Visit India, Getting Here Around and Sample Itineraries
3. Use of Maps, pictures of cultural, religious, places and illustrations are there.

SPECIAL FEATURES

1. UP-TO-DATE COVERAGE
2. DETAILED MAPS
3. GORGEOUS PHOTOS AND ILLUSTRATED FEATURES
4. ITINERARIES AND TOP RECOMMENDATIONS
5. INDISPENSABLE TRIP PLANNING TOOLS

FORMAT

1. Book is available in paperback form and as well as ebook form.
2. This is a single volume book.
3. Book was available in sample trial
4. In sample trial fonts were legible
5. Detailed maps and concise descriptions

Drawbacks

1. There was no mobile application.

Conclusion

Fodor's Essential India helps for planning for a perfect trip. It helps descriptions cover the major sight and give enough details for maximum possibilities of travel. Fodor's Essential India provide putting stars on highly recommended sights. Perhaps it would be best to decide what to see and then use other books for more details when visiting specific sights. This helps to plan trips as per one's taste with providing means to travel whether use to railways, airways, buses or travel by own and hire a driver for the movement purpose.